

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KELLY****FIRST NAME: WILLIAM****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author did use Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author did use Grammarly Premium
The author used the following software (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

PLAGIARISM

1) INTRODUCTION

In the academic world, plagiarism is defined as the intentional or unintentional misappropriation of other author's works and passing that work off as one's own efforts. (cf. Eret and Gokmenoglu 2010; Bailey 2011; Neuman 2011; Selemani, Chawinga, and Dube 2018). That such misappropriation may have been unintended lessens the sanction, not, the seriousness of the plagiarism.

Having sampled a cohort of professional academics; Eret and Gokmenoglu, found varying degrees of understanding, aptitude, and compliance concerning plagiarism leading them to state that "it is really crucial to be well-informed on this topic to prevent the problem and to stick to the ethical norms" (2010, 3303). While Neuman (2011, 545), characterises plagiarism as a "serious form of cheating", Bailey, brings gravity to the situation, stating that plagiarism is "a kind of theft" (2011, 30). More recently, a White Paper published by Turnitin (2016), and a study conducted by (Selemani, Chawinga, and Dube 2018) reinforce the notion that plagiarism is academically unacceptable. Guided principally by Turnitin (2016), it now appears through the advent of technology and the heightened awareness of educators, that plagiarism is both a frequent and detectable phenomenon. It is therefore not out of place to see plagiarism cited as "a serious academic offense" (EUCLID 2019, 5), which academics should make every effort to avoid. The authors noted above are accurate in their comments and sound in the position they have adopted. However, they appear to have overlooked an opportunity to comment on a crucial point, namely, that of 'competency', or said more precisely, that of a professionals' competency which rests upon or flows from, their academic knowledge. Accordingly, this response paper outlines a case suggesting that plagiarism is more than an academic offence. The premise here is that if or when undetected plagiarism can have ramifications far beyond academia.

2) **FACTORS WHICH CONTRIBUTE TO PLAGIARISM**

Liking as I do, a measure of certainty, on first reading Bailey's use of the phrase, '...kind of theft...' (2011, 30) was a 'little annoying'. That said, I doubt if Bailey intended to infer that any measure of uncertainty surrounds the topic of plagiarism. Rather, Bailey is, I think, attempting to draw attention to the fact that there are levels of plagiarism, demarcated by intent, which are not always plainly evident. Broadly, these degrees, which may be indicative of a students' intent, are in the literature conceptualised as either "intentional or unintentional" (Selemani, Chawinga, and Dube 2018, 1). "Intent matters" (Turnitin 2016, 7) and matters for several reasons, some of which will be explored next.

i) *Plagiarism and Intent*

Intentional plagiarism, which has more gravitas, is tantamount to "student dishonesty" (Eret and Gokmenoglu 2010). While limited, there are reports of intentional plagiarism leading to academic dismissal (Neuman 2011, 544).

In reporting on the range of plagiaristic practices, Turnitin, exemplify several practices by demarcating each with a label (2016). The label, "Clone" (Turnitin 2016, 4) characterises the practice by which students knowingly copy verbatim another's work and submit that work, in its entirety, as their own original piece of work. A similar practice, although found to have a marginally lower level of prevalence, labelled "CTRL-C" (*ibid*) which is a keyboard shortcut for 'Copy', was equally noted. During "CTRL-C", students knowingly copy large sections of another's work and without proper citation, again submit such work as their own. A third category label "Find-Replace" (*ibid*) is on the matter of intent, also telling in so much that only "key words and phrases" are changed. In any of these practices, students knowingly submit work which is not theirs. One must assume that the efforts to disguise the act cannot be anything but intentional.

To make a case for plagiarism having ramifications beyond academia, a link between such intentional practices and the ensuing professional competency, can be made. Say for example, that I wish to be a botanist, and I managed to somehow "Clone" or, "CTRL-C" or "Find-Replace" my way through all or a significant portion of my academic career. At the outset of my career as a botanist, at worst, I may hurt some plants. However, what if I aspire to be, say, a counsellor or a pharmacist, or an aeronautical engineer, or any career wherein the health and wellbeing of others is central to the profession. What harms might ensue had I somehow managed to "Clone", "CTRL-C", "Find-Replace" my way through my academic work? Would I have the competency to serve my community or the public at large? More importantly, would I have the competency to know when I cannot serve? Integrity and ethic are twin pillars of professional practice, the foundations and shape of which, I would argue, are established in academia.

A second variation of plagiarism covered in the literature and referred to as unintentional (Eret and Gokmenoglu 2010; Bailey 2011; Selemani, Chawinga, and Dube 2018) is an area that warrants particular focus. The Turnitin White Paper, reasons, and sub-categorises this area under the following labels: "Remix; Recycle; Hybrid; Mashup; 404

Error; Aggregator; Re-Tweet" (Turnitin 2016, 4). In brief, those designations cover the following more frequently encountered practices: paraphrasing and combining from several sources making them fit together thus retaining the critical sentiments but omitting several citations; reusing one's own previously submitted work; combining several sources without any conventional or proper citation; citing non-existent studies or sources; linking and accurately citing multiple sources but with no new or original effort or content included. While not stated in the White paper, there is a possibility that these categories will in places, overlap. The practices noted in Turnitin, tend to be associated with the student experiences of, hurriedness; familial or academic pressures; the pressures to achieve high grades; uncertainty on the matter of plagiarism; or an overestimation of academic writing ability. Even so, (Eret and Gokmenoglu 2010; Turnitin 2016), state that these can in part be lessened by a clear understanding of the relevant university's policies and procedures concerning plagiarism; and or in part by the introduction of classes designed to "teach advanced academic writing such as summarising, synthesising and, referencing" (Selemani, Chawinga, and Dube 2018, 13).

Should the practices noted by Turnitin become persistent in a student's life, vital educational components linked to professional practice are, missed. Under such circumstances, it remains hard to see how any useful, serviceable, or original learning occurs. Therefore, while tentative at this point, the premise linking academic performance with professional competency, even in cases of unintentional plagiarism, remains plausible. While the degree of intent varies, the impact of plagiarism, at least for those we serve, or those we represent, potentially remains the same.

ii) *Paraphrasing*

Unlike the "Remix" (Turnitin 2011,4) variant noted above, "Paraphrasing" (EUCLID 2019, 8) is the accepted convention of taking the core sentiments of another author and restating them in different words while maintaining the integrity of what the original author meant, and having accomplished that; it must be cited (Neuman 2011). In academic terms, paraphrasing is not nearly as easy as it sounds. If it is to be effective, it is essential to comprehend both the context and content which the original author was seeking to convey. It seems safe to say that if I have not grasped the material, it is doubtful that I would be able to paraphrase it accurately. Where paraphrasing becomes problematic, occasionally leading to unintentional plagiarism, is that students such as I, are rightly expected to read, distil, synthesise, and apply some measure of understanding to a vast quantity of material. For my part, I support paraphrasing with notes which aim to capture the source and importance of the context and content, and, my own reflections or responses to what I have read. Where possible, I use software such as Zotero or RefWorks. However, importing some source materials may contravene copyright, or the material in question may simply not be importable. As a result, notes become the handwritten variety. Under those circumstances', notes can pose a risk in so much that the handwritten type may not always be linked back to a source document; as such, no reference point for the note may exist. That, I think, is where unintentional plagiarism may begin to creep in. Reading and noting without a strategy linked to writing, is symbolic of perhaps being a little disorganised, which is to suppose that, notes are in some way an essential part of the bigger

and more organised writing process. Equally, and pertinent to the topic of paraphrasing is the arena of exposure, or to be precise 'self-exposure'. By this, I mean, it is possible that in paraphrasing, as in other areas, I may expose to the reader a profound lack of understanding on my part. To write academically or otherwise is after a fashion, to be vulnerable. Being comfortable with and learning from having one's work critiqued is nonetheless part of being a prospective academic.

iii) *Some conventions*

As I begin my doctoral studies, I am watchful of my proneness to excessive and often inaccurate use of commas and apostrophes. Despite looking at that issue several times and seeing it noted (EUCLID 2019, 17-18) I have yet to master it comprehensively. Equally, I need to be mindful of how on occasions, I tend to 'work things out' or 'think things out' at the abstract or conceptual level. When this creeps into my writing and leads to excessive wordiness, it can be a problem. Excessive wordiness may cloud clarity or weaken the argument, which is odd because clarity and precision is what I am trying to achieve. As such, neither poor grammar nor 'musings' as a previous lecture of mine once called it, are conducive to clear and hopefully somewhat logical, well-rounded academic writing. Indirectly linked to paraphrasing (and by extension to plagiarism) is the substantive issue of discussion, which would be the norm in academic writing. "Take the views you are discussing seriously" (EUCLID 2019, 15) is a sound principle, in so much as to use authors or materials which only support my position is to run the risk of being charged with biased or prejudicial writing. Accordingly, it is not just possible, it is in many ways obligatory, to seek, find, understand, and debate, vigorously, even passionately, but always respectfully. Irrespective of the subject matter, it is only when I have found, heard and understood the opposing side of the argument, can I see how other academics arrived at the position, opinions, or conclusions they have. From this it follows, that opposing or contrary views must be sought and considered.

Beyond the issue of commas and apostrophes, which require constant monitoring, and beyond the convention of a strong, but consistent and reasoned debate, which may be of value, in the following section, I survey an additional facets of academic writing.

iv) *Does style matter?*

To be honest, before viewing the Basic ACA-401 Tutorial video (EUCLID n.d.), 'style' would not have been something that I had considered or appreciated. That is not to imply that I now understand the topic, but more to say that I found the instruction, helpful if a little challenging.

Matching the videos' content with the materials in (EUCLID 2019) leads to the conclusion that the term 'style' in academic writing has several meanings, some of which are known as 'Paper style', 'Writing style', 'House style', and perhaps 'others' which I have yet to discover. However, what is new to me is the notion of what is termed 'house style' as in, the World Health Organisation (WHO) house style. To make a similar point to the one noted at (EUCLID 2019, 35), I will use my date of birth, which, in WHO house style,

would appear as 06 July 1965 (WHO 2013, 27). As such, WHO house style, leaves no room for any ambiguity. In British English, I have encountered that same date, in numeral form appear as, 6/7/1965. Whereas in the American English numeral form, it appears as, 7/6/1965, which if read from a British English perspective, would appear to add one month to my age. While all three mean and reference the same thing (a date), there are outward differences. Such differences are not the issue; consistency is. Should all three be used interchangeably in the same text, it not only distracts readers, but it highlights inconsistencies within the paper, making the paper difficult to follow, and any meaning therein tricky to grasp. When used with liberal interchangeability, any paper may come across as incoherent, when in fact it may be coherent, just poorly detailed, and organised. A coherent argument in the writers' mind, may, through writing inconsistency, come across as incoherent.

The skill therefore is I think twofold; firstly, in order to fit consistently into both the paper and the broader house style, the skill is in adjusting the writing and thinking styles of the author. Which by inference may require learning or conversely, unlearning some writing or thinking habits which undermine consistency and coherence. Secondly, knowing that, content, paper style, and the broader house style tend to a measure of specificity, the skill is in understanding the readers' reading points of reference is equally essential. From this it follows, that writers must consider readers. Superordinate to these, is the premise of accuracy, which links back to intentional and or unintentional plagiarism.

Considering the above, it follows that if asked the question of, "Does style matter"? The answer must be "yes".

v) *Ethic*

Academic writing can be considered the product of some form of research or enquiry. In that light, research, and writing, share a set of, norms. Good academic writing, like research, is not easy. It is a language with principles and conventions, chief of which is ethic.

The constellation, 'truthfulness, honesty, principle, accountability, responsibility, answerability', plus more besides could in ways be seen as being symbolic of, or even the hallmarks of, or even suitable substitutes for, the phrase 'ethic'. Without oblique configuration, the word 'right', does not appear in the constellation. Writing, therefore is not about right, or being right, words akin to power. No, to my mind writing is more akin to value. It should in ways, add value to the broader body of knowledge, and when plagiarised, that simply can not happen.

Notwithstanding my eagerness as a new student, it would be rash to ignore the ethics of academic writing, to do so is to risk the charge of plagiarism being, levelled. Aside from style, it would be equally foolhardy to ignore the broader conventions of writing which support respectful scholarly and hopefully persuasive debate.

3) CONCLUSION

To be taken seriously, academics approach the topic of writing seriously. Moreover, while they may call upon the words and or works of others to support or contradict a position or an idea, they do so knowingly, fittingly and, within strict conventions. In and of itself that sentiment is what prompted the core of this response paper. It is nevertheless, sensible to forcefully remind myself of the issue of plagiarism and risks involved in it. It is equally timely to remind myself of the context specific and nuanced skills which writers, who aim to write with at least some integrity, must work at gaining. Gaining these is my endeavour.

Writers write for readers. By extrapolation, it could be said that academic writers write for academic readers. Be that as it may, that linear view fails to capture, that sometimes writers, academic or otherwise, in writing, put to words, the voice or lived experiences of those less fortunate, which makes writing, a privilege.

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